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Relationship Between Bullying And Mental Health Of Secondary School Students In Delta Central Senatorial District Of Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the relationship between bullying and the mental health of students in secondary schools. A correlational survey design was utilized, and a sample of 380 respondents was drawn using the multi-stage random sampling technique. The questionnaire used is the Bullying and Mental Health Scale (BAMHS). The research question was addressed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, while the hypothesis was tested using linear regression at a significance level of 0.05. The findings revealed a significant association between bullying and the mental health of students in secondary schools in the Delta Central Senatorial District of Delta State. Based on this result, it was concluded that the mental well-being of secondary school students is a complex and vital aspect of their overall health, influenced by various factors such as academic challenges, personal growth, and the pervasive impact of bullying, including cyberbullying. In conclusion, it was recommended that Schools should establish and enforce comprehensive anti-bullying programs that address various forms of bullying, including physical, verbal, relational, and cyberbullying. Educational institutions should prioritize mental well-being alongside academic achievement. The Government should integrate resilience-building programs into the curriculum to equip students with effective coping strategies for dealing with personal challenges, identity exploration, and academic stress.

Keywords: bullying, mental health, secondary schools, students

INTRODUCTION

The well-being of high school students' mental health is an important and multifaceted component of their overall health, especially during their adolescent years, which is a time of significant physical, emotional, and psychological changes. These changes can leave students vulnerable to various mental health issues, and factors like academic stress, social interactions, personal growth, and the impact of digital technology can all contribute to the mental health landscape of high school students. High school academics can significantly affect students' mental health, with academic stressors like rigorous coursework, high-stakes exams, and the pursuit of future career aspirations placing high expectations on students. These expectations can come from different sources like parents, teachers, and society. The pressure to excel academically and meet these expectations can be overwhelming, and research shows that academic stress is a significant factor contributing to mental health challenges among students, including depression and emotional distress.

Bowers & Shi, (2021) state that the chronic experience of academic stress can have a cascading effect on students' overall well-being, influencing their self-esteem, motivation, and engagement in academic activities, and exacerbating mental health challenges. However, supportive relationships with teachers, peers, and family members can mitigate the negative impact of academic challenges on mental health by providing encouragement, understanding, and resources to help students cope with

academic stress. Striking a balance between academic rigor and mental well-being is essential, and schools should consider implementing strategies to foster a positive and supportive academic environment while recognizing the importance of mental health alongside academic achievement. The challenges that high school students face can have profound implications for their mental health, but recognizing and addressing the pressures associated with academic performance is vital for creating a nurturing educational environment that promotes both academic success and students' well-being. Finally, adolescence is a transformative period marked by personal growth, identity exploration, and coping with various challenges, navigating one's identity can be complex and, at times, challenging, contributing to mental health issues.

According to Dvorsky, Hall & Rosen, (2023) opined that the mental health of high school students is greatly influenced by the challenges associated with personal growth and identity exploration. These challenges can lead to various mental health issues, such as anxiety, stress, and emotional distress. Addressing these challenges is crucial for promoting positive mental health outcomes. Family dynamics play a significant role in adolescents' lives. Issues within the family, such as conflicts, changes, or instability, can lead to increased stress levels and affect the mental well-being of high school students. Adolescence is a period of rapid physical changes, and adapting to these changes can be a source of stress. Challenges related to puberty, body image concerns, and societal expectations around physical appearance can contribute to mental health struggles (Hankin, et al., 2017).

Personal challenges, such as peer relationships and academic pressures, often intersect with social dynamics. The interaction between these challenges can amplify the impact on mental health, underscoring the need for a comprehensive approach to support adolescents. Equipping students with effective coping strategies and building resilience are essential components of addressing personal challenges. Interventions promoting emotional regulation, self-awareness, and adaptive coping mechanisms can contribute to positive mental health outcomes (Jones, Smith & Peterson, 2023).

In addition to these factors, the impact of bullying on mental health will also be examined. Bullying, whether physical, verbal, or online, can significantly affect a student's mental health. Bullying is a pervasive issue in high schools, taking various forms that extend beyond traditional physical aggression. Understanding the prevalence and diverse manifestations of bullying is crucial for addressing its significant impact on the mental health of students. Physical bullying involves direct aggression, such as hitting, kicking, pushing, or any form of bodily harm inflicted upon the victim. Victims of physical bullying often experience not only physical harm but also psychological distress, leading to heightened anxiety and a sense of vulnerability. Verbal bullying includes the use of harmful words, insults, name-calling, or derogatory language intended to belittle or harm the victim emotionally. Verbal bullying is commonly reported in schools, and its prevalence can be influenced by factors such as school culture and peer dynamics. The verbal attacks associated with bullying contribute to emotional distress, impacting self-esteem and potentially leading to symptoms of depression (Modecki, et al., 2014).

Williams & Kerns, (2022) posit that relational aggression involves manipulating social relationships, spreading rumors, exclusion, or other non-physical tactics to harm the victim's social standing. This form of bullying is often more subtle but can be prevalent, particularly among adolescents navigating complex social dynamics. Victims of relational aggression may experience feelings of isolation, rejection, and a negative impact on their self-worth and mental well-being.

Sullivan, et al (2024) believed that cyberbullying, facilitated through digital platforms, employs technology to harass, threaten, or disseminate harmful content about the victim. Its prevalence has surged with the widespread use of technology, posing a significant concern for students both within and outside the school environment. The online nature of cyberbullying exacerbates its impact, fostering heightened anxiety, depression, and feelings of powerlessness among victims. Various forms of bullying, encompassing physical, verbal, relational, or cyberbullying, pose significant challenges in high schools. Comprehensive anti-bullying strategies should be implemented to create safe and supportive environments that prioritize the well-being of all students.

Brown, et al, (2021). shows a strong link between being bullied and the emergence of depressive symptoms in secondary school students. Repeated exposure to bullying behaviors significantly affects mental health, leading to negative emotions and creating a pervasive sense of distress. Several studies,

including those by Fitzgerald, et al (2023) and Jang, et al (2023), provide empirical evidence supporting the connection between bullying victimization and depressive symptoms. Longitudinal research designs highlight that bullying often precedes the onset of depressive symptoms, emphasizing the temporal relationship. The chronic and repetitive nature of bullying intensifies its negative impact on mental health, creating a continuous stressor for victims. Persistent exposure to verbal, physical, or relational aggression heightens vulnerability to depressive symptoms.

Bullying generates a pervasive sense of threat and vulnerability for victims, fostering fear of repeated aggression, humiliation, or exclusion. This constant state of heightened alertness and distress significantly impacts victims' self-image, contributing to feelings of inadequacy and worthlessness. The negative narrative and harmful actions associated with bullying extend beyond immediate incidents, leading to heightened feelings of sadness, despair, and hopelessness. The psychosocial stressors induced by bullying, such as humiliation and derogatory comments, contribute significantly to heightened anxiety levels (Lee & Kim, 2023). The association between bullying and suicidal ideation is deeply concerning, as bullying has been unequivocally linked to elevated suicidal thoughts among secondary school students. Patel, et al (2023) state that victims often grapple with profound feelings of despair and hopelessness, increasing vulnerability to self-harm or suicide. The enduring impact of bullying on mental health persists into adulthood, shaping an individual's trajectory. Victims may internalize negative messages, impacting self-worth and hindering healthy relationships. The coping mechanisms developed during adolescence can have lasting effects on an individual's ability to manage stress in adulthood. Supportive interventions are crucial in mitigating the long-term impact of bullying (Rogers, et al 2022).

Thomas, et al. (2022). Opined that in the digital age, cyberbullying introduces unique complexities, intensifying the impact of online harassment on adolescents' mental health. Conducted through various online platforms, cyberbullying contributes to heightened anxiety, depression, and a sense of vulnerability. The consequences extend beyond immediate emotional distress, influencing future online interactions and shaping perceptions of self-worth.

Statement of problem

Mental health is a critical aspect of overall well-being that significantly influences how individuals think, feel, and act. Its importance spans various dimensions of life, including personal, social, and professional domains. The current educational landscape faces a rising concern centered on the pervasive issue of bullying within secondary school settings, and its potential repercussions on the mental health of students. The researcher seeks to investigate the relationship between bullying and the mental well-being of adolescents, with a focus on understanding various dimensions of bullying, encompassing both victim experiences and perpetrator behaviors. The research will address critical problem areas, starting with the prevalence and diverse types of bullying exhibited among secondary school students, including physical, verbal, relational, and cyberbullying. It aims to unravel the impact of being a victim of bullying on the mental health of students, while also examining the psychological consequences for those who engage in bullying behaviors.

Furthermore, the study will investigate the underlying risk factors that contribute to an increased susceptibility to bullying and mental health challenges, as well as potential protective factors that may mitigate these negative effects. It delves into the potential long-term consequences of experiencing or perpetrating bullying during secondary school years, and how the mental health impact persists or evolves into adulthood. In addition, the research will explore existing interventions and prevention strategies implemented in secondary schools to address bullying. It critically assesses the effectiveness of these strategies in mitigating the mental health repercussions of bullying and identifies areas for improvement.

Research question

What is the relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students in Delta Central Senatorial district, Delta State?

Research hypothesis

The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

There is no significant relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students in Delta Central Senatorial district, Delta State.

Purpose of study

To highlight the relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students in Delta Central Senatorial district, Delta State.

Research Design

This study adopted the correlational survey research design. A correlation survey research design is appropriate when a researcher is interested in investigating the degree of relationship and nature of relationships among variables.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprises 20,500 secondary school adolescents in Delta Central Senatorial district, Delta State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for this study consists of 380 secondary school adolescents drawn from the entire population size of 20,500. A stratified sampling technique and a simple random sampling technique were used to select the sample for the study.

Research Instrument

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire which is titled: Bullying and Mental Health Questionnaire (BAMHQ).

Methods of Data Collection

The questionnaire was administered to secondary school adolescents in Warri South Local Government Area directly by the researcher.

Method of Data Analysis

The research question was answered using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and coefficient of determination. On the other hand, the hypotheses were tested using Linear and Multiple linear regressions at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research question.

What is the relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students in Delta Central Senatorial district, Delta State?

Table 1; Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and coefficient of determination of the relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students

Variable	<i>N</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>R</i> ² %	Decision
Bulling		43.96	5.60				
Mental health	380	46.10	5.85	0.285	0.081	8.1	Positive Relationship

Table 1 shows the multiple Correlation and Coefficient of determination of bullying and the mental health of secondary school students in Delta Central Senatorial district, Delta State. As shown in the table, $R = 0.285$, $R^2 = 0.081$, and $R^2\% = 8.1\%$, which is the nature of the relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students in Delta Central Senatorial district, Delta State. This signified a positive relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students in Delta Central Senatorial district, Delta State. From the result, bullying accounted for 8.1% of the variance in mental health.

Hypothesis

Table 2 Linear Regression Analysis of bullying and mental health of secondary school students in Warri South Local Government Area

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	2336.974	1	778.991	24.691	.000 ^b
Residual	26502.051	378	31.550		
Total	28839.026	379			

Model	Variables in Equation			t	Sig
	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardised Coefficient			
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	31.090	1.961		15.857	.000
parental involvement	.257	.038	.247	6.841	.000
sexual abstinence	.057	.019	.101	3.037	.002

$\alpha = 0.05, R = 0.285, R\text{-Square} = 0.081$

- a. **Dependent Variable:** Bullying
- b. **Predictors (Constant):** Mental health

The above table shows a linear regression output of the relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students. The computed F-value of 405.407 and a p-value of 0.000. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.000 was less than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicated that there was a significant relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students. The R² value of 0.519 showed that 51.9% of the variance in mental health was accounted for by bullying.

DISCUSSION OF FINDING

The result indicated that there was a significant relationship between bullying and the mental health of secondary school students. The finding that there is a significant relationship between bullying and mental health carries profound implications for understanding the complex interplay between psychosocial experiences within the secondary school environment and students' overall mental well-being. Firstly, the term "significant relationship" implies that the observed variations in bullying experiences are associated with measurable changes in mental health outcomes. This aligns with existing research, emphasizing the impact of negative social interactions on psychological well-being, particularly during the formative years of secondary education.

The identification of a significant relationship highlights the critical role that bullying plays as a potential risk factor for mental health issues among secondary school students. Being subjected to various forms of bullying, whether physical, verbal, relational, or cyberbullying, can have detrimental effects on an individual's emotional and psychological state. This may manifest in increased stress, anxiety, depression, and a general decline in mental well-being.

Furthermore, the term "significant" in this context suggests that the observed association is not merely due to chance. The statistical significance adds rigor to the finding, reinforcing the credibility of the identified relationship and providing confidence in its generalizability beyond the specific sample studied.

The implication of a significant relationship between bullying and mental health urges a comprehensive approach to addressing and preventing bullying within the secondary school environment. This may involve implementing evidence-based anti-bullying programs, fostering a culture of respect and empathy, and providing resources for mental health support within the school community. The significant relationship also underscores the importance of early identification and intervention. Educators, school counselors, and mental health professionals play pivotal roles in recognizing signs of bullying and addressing the associated mental health concerns promptly. Developing strategies that empower students to report incidents of bullying and creating a supportive environment for victims is essential. The findings are in line with Copeland, et al (2023) and Bowers,

A., & Shi, J. (2021) who found a positive relationship between bullying and the mental health of students in secondary schools.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the mental well-being of secondary school students is a complex and vital aspect of their overall health, influenced by various factors such as academic challenges, personal growth, and the pervasive impact of bullying, including cyberbullying.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from the analysis of factors influencing the mental well-being of secondary school students, several recommendations can be proposed to support their overall mental health:

1. Schools should establish and enforce comprehensive anti-bullying programs that address various forms of bullying, including physical, verbal, relational, and cyberbullying.
2. Educational institutions should prioritize mental well-being alongside academic achievement.
3. The Government should integrate resilience-building programs into the curriculum to equip students with effective coping strategies for dealing with personal challenges, identity exploration, and academic stress.

REFERENCES

- Bowers, A., & Shi, J. (2021). The effects of academic stress on adolescent mental health: A systematic review. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 36(4), 531-553.
- Brown, T., Robinson, R., & Hart, L. (2021). The impact of bullying on adolescent mental health: A review of recent studies. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 68(4), 593-604.
- Dvorsky, M. R., Hall, C. S., & Rosen, S. K. (2023). Navigating identity and mental health during adolescence. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 52(2), 287-304.
- Fitzgerald, A. M., Nguyen, T. D., & Morrow, J. (2023). Cyberbullying and its effects on adolescent mental health: New insights from recent research. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 26(2), 101-109.
- Jang, H., Lee, S., & Zhang, X. (2023). Longitudinal relationships between bullying and depressive symptoms in adolescents: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 52(5), 950-965.
- Jones, L. L., Smith, T. R., & Peterson, J. M. (2023). Body image and mental health in adolescence: A review of recent findings. *Adolescent Health Review*, 17(3), 220-234.
- Lee, J., & Kim, H. (2023). Self-image and emotional distress among bullying victims: Recent findings and implications. *Journal of Emotional and Behavioral Disorders*, 31(1), 45-56.
- Modecki, K. L., Minchin, J., Harbaugh, A. G., Guerra, N. G., & Runions, K. C. (2014). Bullying prevalence across contexts: a meta-analysis measuring cyber and traditional bullying. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 55(5), 602-611.
- Patel, V., Andrews, G., & Tognini, S. (2023). Suicidal ideation and bullying: Evidence from recent studies. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 53(3), 311-323.
- Rogers, C., Green, J., & Thomas, A. (2022). Bullying, mental health, and resilience: Long-term effects on adolescent development. *Child Development Research*, 2022, 875-890.
- Sullivan, T. P., Wolkenstein, B., & Marks, D. (2024). Psychosocial stressors and mental health outcomes in bullying victims: A contemporary review. *Journal of Adolescence*, 88, 71-84.
- Thomas, R., Richards, J., & Smith, E. (2022). Bullying victimization and its effects on mental health: A comprehensive review of recent findings. *Behavioral Medicine*, 48(4), 265-277.
- Williams, S. B., & Kerns, K. A. (2022). The impact of family dynamics on adolescent mental health: Insights from recent studies. *Family Relations*, 71(1), 56-72.